

Deliverable D.1.1.1

Selection and evaluation protocol (draft) for prioritisation of digital archival

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H-SEARCH
Heritage Science Elastic Archives

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The archives of the Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage (KIK-IRPA) can be subdivided into two main categories: institutional archives and scientific archives. The latter, which are the subject of the H-SEARCH project, currently consist of more than 20.000 individual intervention dossiers that can take the form of a physical folder, a digital folder on the institutional network or both (hybrid). Nowadays, only 5% of the intervention dossiers are available in a digital format.

1. RECENT INITIATIVES IN THE DIGITAL ARCHIVING OF SCIENTIFIC INTERVENTION DOSSIERS

In recent years, a number of initiatives have been launched to digitise the physical intervention dossiers or to archive the digital-born ones. Since with current resources, digitising and archiving the entire scientific archive of the institution would take several decades, choices had to be made and the criteria for selecting dossiers varied from one initiative to another.

In the frame of the DIGIT program, 231 physical intervention dossiers were digitised. In consultation with the heads of the workshops and laboratories, these dossiers have been selected because they pertain to significant works of Belgian heritage, are frequently consulted both internally and externally, or required urgent digital duplication due to their poor state of preservation.

The opportunity to outsource the digitisation of the dossiers, thereby enabling a significant increase in the number of files that could be made available online via the BALaT knowledge platform, led the DIGIT project managers to adopt a completely different selection criterion¹. Indeed, the focus was placed on paper files from the Monuments Lab (1968–2007), primarily due to their standardised format and the homogeneity of their medium. So far, over 1.000 of these dossiers have been digitised and many more will be in the coming months.

Many physical intervention dossiers are also digitised by the “dossier team” of the Documentation Department in response to consultation requests from external users.

As part of the HESCIDA project, 430 closed digital-born intervention dossiers have been aggregated, organised and documented in a “pre-archive” hosted on the institutional network share (fileserver)². The primary prioritisation criterion for selecting the dossiers was completeness, which led to a preference for intervention dossiers from the painting, monuments, paper and textile laboratories, as well as those from the imagery unit.

The pre-archive, which increases in size daily by the ingestion of new and old digital-born dossiers but also by the gradual integration of the above-mentioned digitised dossiers, will be taken as a basis for the preservation and archiving actions described in WP 2. This is why, in order for its content to meet all the challenges raised by the H-SEARCH project, it

¹ <https://balat.kikirpa.be/>

² Project FSIRI/00/HE1 - Heritage Science Data Archive (<http://hescida.kikirpa.be>)

seemed necessary to establish a selection protocol that would allow to identify the closed intervention dossiers for which digitisation, archiving and dissemination will be prioritised.

2. PRELIMINARY LIST OF SELECTION CRITERIA

A preliminary list of selection prioritisation criteria has been drawn up (D.1.1.1). These criteria, currently numbering nine, are intended to identify a set of dossiers best suited to achieving the objectives of the H-SEARCH project and even other highly complementary projects currently underway at KIK-IRPA. They will enable the collection of a sufficiently broad sample to be representative of all scenarios in the processing of closed intervention dossiers, as well as of KIK-IRPA in all its multiple components.

1. **Heritage value of the object:** Heritage objects of special interest or exceptional importance because of their archaeological, historical, aesthetic or scientific value have been selected by the Belgian regional institutions and entered in lists, registers or databases that can be consulted online³. Priority will be given to the intervention dossiers related to these objects.
2. **Scientific value of the heritage item:** Priority will also be given to intervention dossiers with high scientific potential, in other words records containing data sets which may be used in future research or related to heritage objects which have the potential to yield crucial information.
3. **User needs:** Strong focus should be given on digitisation and archiving of items for which there is a direct evidence of demand. About 500 intervention dossiers are consulted annually on site in the Information Centre. The Excel file recording the number and the type of dossiers that are consulted by internal and external clients will prove to be a valuable tool for setting priorities.
4. **Condition of originals:** Priority should also be given to dossiers in a poor or vulnerable condition. This not only creates a digital backup of the physical dossier that could disappear, but also preserves the original physical record by minimising the risk of deterioration from handling.
5. **Extent of the intervention:** Identifying items that have undergone significant interventions, whether through restoration in a workshop and/or laboratory analyses, should make it possible to select dossiers containing sufficiently extensive and representative datasets that reflect the wide range of treatments and analyses that can be provided by the institution.

³ Flemish government list of acknowledged rare and essential cultural objects in Flanders: <https://topstukken.vlaanderen.be/topstukken/>. Wallonia-Brussels federation list of mobile cultural heritage (treasures, goods of patrimonial interest and religious heritage) in Wallonia and Brussels: <https://patrimoineculturel.cfwb.be/patrimoines-en%20fwb/patrimoinesenfwbinventairedupatrimoinemobilier/>. Brussels Government inventory of the movable and immaterial heritage of the Brussels Capital Region: <http://patrimoine.brussels/decouvrir/inventaires-du-patrimoine-bruxellois>. Databases of protected or inventoried immovable heritage can be found on the following websites : <https://inventaris.onroerenderfgoed.be/> (Flanders), <http://patrimoine.brussels/decouvrir/registre-du-patrimoine-protege> (Brussels Capital), https://lampspw.wallonie.be/dgo4/site_thema/index.php and https://lampspw.wallonie.be/dgo4/site_ipic/index.php/presentation/index (Wallonia). A list of Wallonia's exceptional immovable heritage can also be consulted online: <https://wallex.wallonie.be/eli/arrete/2022/05/12/2022032365/2022/06/20>

6. **Completeness of the intervention dossiers:** The dossiers which are to be transmitted to the archive should be as complete as possible. A list of data objects was drawn up in order to ensure that old and new intervention dossiers are conform to what the archive expects.
7. **Exhaustiveness:** The selection should best reflect the scientific activities of the Institute and, to this end, intervention dossiers from each cell (laboratories and workshops) must be selected.
8. **Possibility to outsource the digitization of intervention dossiers:** Engaging an external service provider can help accelerate the digitisation process of dossiers. However, this outsourcing is mainly suitable for dossiers with a standard format and homogeneous medium, such as paper documents in A4 format.
9. **Relationship to complementary projects:** Priority must also be given to intervention dossiers that are essential for the successful completion of related projects conducted by KIK-IRPA. For instance, dossiers that, within the framework of the DIGILAB.be project⁴, could be enriched with heritage science datasets from other institutions.

The catalogue of selection criteria presented above is far from closed or set in stone. Compiling the list of intervention dossiers that will be handled during the project for evaluating the archival procedure and analysing them could lead to the identification of previously unnoticed criteria.

3. LIST OF DOSSIERS FOR EVALUATING THE ARCHIVAL PROCEDURES (D.1.2.1)

The H-SEARCH project pursues a twofold objective: to define and implement strategies and workflows that ensure both the long-term archival of research and its alignment with FAIR principles. These workflows must accommodate the diverse range of intervention dossiers. To achieve this, a representative selection of 200 dossiers will be identified based on defined criteria and the existing variability. This set, forming deliverable D.1.2.1, will comprise an equal distribution of digitally born and scanned dossiers.

A first list of intervention dossiers to be given priority was started on the basis of inventories produced by the Wallonia-Brussel federation⁵. This list includes works of art classified by the Belgian regional institution for which the KIK-IRPA has intervention dossiers. The application of two additional selection criteria to this list, specifically the extent and completeness of the dossiers (criteria 5 and 6), allowed for further refinement, retaining only those most relevant to the project. Conversely, in the near future, when viewed through the lens of criterion 9, this list could be expanded to include intervention dossiers that might benefit from the heritage science datasets provided by the partners involved in the DIGILAB.be project.

⁴ Project EF/231/DIGILAB.be: DIGILAB Belgian Federated Repositories.

⁵ Wallonia-Brussels federation list of mobile cultural heritage (treasures, goods of patrimonial interest and religious heritage) in Wallonia and Brussels: https://patrimoineculturel.cfwb.be/patrimoinesen%20fwb/patrimoinesenfwbinventairedupatrimoine_mobilier/.

In the coming months, this selection process will be extended to all existing Belgian heritage inventories.

Another list comprises intervention dossiers from different workshops and laboratories (glass and ceramics, metals, stone sculpture, and polychrome wood sculpture), all following a standardized format and uniform medium, making them suitable for digitisation by an external service provider (criterion 8).